

H-Ast_Ependymal time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 6

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 983

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 307

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 2134

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 4

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 1931

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 822

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 3

H-BG time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 41

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1388

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 25

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 592

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1041

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 7

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 971

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 919

H-BS_Choroid_Ependymal time clusters

H-eCN_UBC time clusters

H-Endothelial time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 3029

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 3915

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 3

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 1373

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 1511

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 96

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1281

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 5

H-GN time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1129

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 28

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 39

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 45

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 10

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 447

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1352

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 2155

H-iCN time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1318

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 720

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 974

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 2037

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 224

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 420

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1000

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 1683

H-PC time clusters

Cluster 1. Number of genes: 1764

Cluster 2. Number of genes: 1686

Cluster 3. Number of genes: 151

Cluster 4. Number of genes: 2573

Cluster 5. Number of genes: 116

Cluster 6. Number of genes: 813

Cluster 7. Number of genes: 1025

Cluster 8. Number of genes: 208

